

DISCIPLINE TECHNIQUES OF PARENTS AN SMART IDEA TOWARD RESPONSIBLE PARENTHOOD

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Abstract

Discipline is the most important thing in everyone's life without discipline one cannot live a happy life. It is an act of living life following the rule and regulation. But, everyone should have self-discipline because it is important to achieve complete discipline in life and it also helps to develop better character of the person. This study aims to determine the discipline techniques of parents to their children. It includes 45 respondents from different barangay of Cabatuan to avoid prejudice of their perceptions. The researchers used quantitative researches were chosen by the process of checklist and survey questionnaire method to support the data collection. The result of the study indicates that parents always teach their children good manners and right conduct in which they want their children to become a respectful person. Further, if you respect oneself and other they will respect you too. However, there are still parents who used physical punishment such as spanking and hitting which it should not be, instead talk calmly to the child to have an understanding. It is therefore, recommended to the children to obey the rules and regulation of parents as well as the teacher to be a good person because if you know what is right over wrong you know what to do.

Keywords: Punishment, Self-Discipline, Self- Control, Will Power.

BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Discipline is a way of guiding; correcting unwanted behavior and helping children learn what morality which defines as doing right and wrong is.

In this world, our parents are the reason why we are here today. They are the parents like no other because they taught us, dressed us, shouted at us, kissed us, but most importantly they loved us unconditionally by means of always been there for to guide us on the right path and correcting our mistakes when we do something wrong that's why there is no enough words to describe how much they mean to us.

Today's generation children knows a lot about something not knowing whether it is good or bad and they become harsh to do such things just maybe because of peer pressure we cannot deny that they trying to tell with their parents to do group projects the fact that they just go somewhere to have fun. When the parent know the truth they

scold their children through spank, shout, yelling, etc. but we can't blame those parents because they just want their children to become a good person, a model to her/his fellow children but it could not be. You should know the right way to punish your children, talk or confront him if ever because once you punish them there is a possibility wherein they do and do it again which it might be their reason to become revile.

Every parent want their children to become well-behaved, honest, responsible, respectful individuals and have a self-discipline because where ever you go you can still use that which your attitude may reflects to your parents because we have here sayings that "Like mother like daughter", "Like father, like son".

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORKS

This study focus on how parents discipline their children. In this study, aside from assessing how parents discipline their children, the researchers attempted to find out whether they discipline through punishment or in a proper way.

Nowadays, many children become hard headed they do such things which we can deny that some has no discipline wherein they do whatever they want just for their happiness. That's why we can't blame some parents who become harsh in disciplining their children wherein they do physical punishment.

Paradigm of the Study

The figure depicts the underlying framework of the study.

The input box includes the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, religion, civil status and home address. The other input includes the discipline techniques of parents.

The process box involves ask permission from the principal to conduct the study, coordinate with the parents to float the questionnaires, retrieval of questionnaires and tabulating the data.

The output area shows the researchers expected outcome is parents discipline their children in a proper way.

This chapter presents the methodology, the respondents, the data gathering instruments, and procedures, and the statistical tool that is use in analyzing and interpreting the needed data in attaining the objectives of the study.

Methods of Research Used

In order to determine the Concept and discipline techniques of parents a smart idea toward responsible parenthood, the researcher use quantitative research. The quantitative research method emphasizes objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data collected through polls, questionnaires, and surveys, or by manipulating pre-existing statistical data using computational techniques.

Respondents of the Study

This study included 45 respondents which are parents from different barangay of cabatuan to avoid prejudice of their perception. The researchers included 20 respondents from diamantina, 8 from caloacan, 6 from tandul, 3 from namnama, del corpus and rang-ay, and 1 from nueva era and culing west. The respondents were chosen selected using Selected Random Method.

Data Gathering Tools

The respondents were chosen by the process of checklist and survey questionnaire method to support the data collection. The first part includes the profile of the respondents such as age, gender, religion, civil status and home address. The second part is all about the discipline techniques of the respondents in terms of personal, educational, family and peers.

Data Gathering Procedure

First, the researchers asked permission from the principal to conduct the study. After the permission is granted, the researcher undertook the following steps:

1. Coordinate with the parents from different barangay of cabatuan by checking the following questions that is all about how they discipline their children.
2. Do the floating of questionnaire to the respondents.
3. Compute, tabulate, analyse, and interpret the data gathered to arrive at the findings of the study.

Statistical Tools Used

In order to analyze the data gathered for this study, the researchers made use of the following statistical tools: Percentage. This tool used to reduce the different sets or number or common frequencies of a comparative sets of number. It is employed as a form of numerical analysis. This is utilized to determine the proportion of the respondents in each category.

Formula:

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100$$

Where:

P=percentage

f=frequency

n=number of respondents

100=constant variable

Likert Scale. This will be used to analyse the answered of the respondents through the questionnaire using the following interpretation Always(5), Often(4), Sometimes(3), Seldom(2), and Never(1).

OPTION	QUANTITATIVE DESCRIPTION	INTERVAL
5	Always	4.20-5.00
4	Often	3.40-4.19
3	Sometimes	2.60-3.39
2	Seldom	1.80- 2.59
1	Never	1.00-1.79

MAJOR RESULTS

This chapter presents the interpretation and analysis of the data gathering using questionnaires that were answered by the respondents of the study.

A. Profile of the Respondents

Table 1

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
31-40	17	37.78
41-50	17	37.78
51-60	10	22.22
61-70	1	2.22
TOTAL	45	100

This table shows that the age 31-40 and 41-50 years old got the highest percentage which gained a percentage of 37.78 and the least was the age of 61-70 years old with 2.22%.

Table 2

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Gender

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Male	10	22.22
Female	35	77.78
TOTAL	45	100

This table shows that majority of the respondents were female with a percentage of 77.78 and the male respondents only got 22.22%.

Table 3

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Religion

RELIGION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Roman Catholic	36	80
Iglesia ni Cristo	3	6.67
Methodist	0	0
Born Again Christian	1	2.22
Baptist	1	2.22
Jehovah Witnesses	0	0

Ispiritista	2	4.44
Others	2	4.44
TOTAL	45	100

This table shows that the highest percentage in the distribution of religion was the Roman Catholic with 80%, and the least was the Methodist and Jehovah Witnesses with 0%.

Table 4

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Civil Status

CIVIL STATUS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Married	43	95.56
Widow	1	2.22
Separated	1	2.22
TOTAL	45	100

This table shows that the married parents got the majority with 43 or 95.56% and the widowed and separated parents are same that only got 2.22%.

Table 5

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Home Address

HOME ADDRESS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Diamantina	20	44.44
Calaocan	8	17.78
Tandul	6	13.33
Namnama	3	6.67
Nueva Era	1	2.22
Del Corpuz	3	6.67
Culing West	1	2.22
Rang-ay	3	6.67
TOTAL	45	100.00

This table shows that majority of the respondents belong to the home address of diamantina with the frequency of 20 or 44.44%, while nueva era and culing west were only got 2.22%.

Table 6

Mean Description of the Respondents' Concept and discipline techniques of parents a smart idea toward responsible parenthood in Terms of Personal Factors

PERSONAL FACTORS	FREQUENCY n=45					MEAN	RANK	DESCRIPTION
	5	4	3	2	1			
1.I scold my children when they didn't follow my command	14	6	22	2	1	3.67	5	Often
2.I didn't tolerate my children when I know that it's their fault	26	2	11	0	6	3.93	2	Often
3.I calmly talk to my children	18	2	20	5	0	3.73	4	Often
4. I teach them good manner and right conduct	42	1	2	0	0	4.89	1	Always
5.My children fight or talk back at me when I discipline them	7	5	15	7	11	2.78	8	Sometimes
6. I didn't allow my children to drink liquor and smoking	28	1	6	0	10	3.82	3	Often
7. I didn't allow my children to go out at night	19	4	10	3	9	3.47	7	Often
8.The punishment I give to my children depends on my mood	8	4	15	6	12	2.78	8	Sometimes
9.I spank my child with my hand when he/she has done something wrong	5	3	12	2	23	2.22	9	Seldom
10. I hit my children with a belt or other object when they have done something wrong	2	2	11	2	28	1.84	11	Seldom
11. I slap my children when they have done something wrong	1	2	10	3	29	1.73	12	Never
12. I take away a privilege or money from my children as a punishment	2	4	9	3	27	1.91	10	Seldom
13.I won't allow my children to go along with the stranger	25	2	5	1	12	3.60	6	Often
Grand Weighted Mean						3.11		Sometimes

This table shows that majority of parents always teach their children good manners with the mean of 4.89 because it is important in one's life, if you respect others then they will respect you too. Followed by which parents often didn't tolerate their children when it is their fault with the total mean of 3.93. It indicates that when

the children commit mistakes parents didn't abide their children fault for them to learn from it and correct their unnecessary behavior.

Furthermore, parents never slap their children when they have done something wrong with the total mean of 1.73 because parents know that it's so very harsh. However, there are still parents who rarely hit and spank the children in which it should not be because they will think that you hated them and that's the time they are going to revile. Teach your kids from right and wrong you don't need to use that punishment.

Table 7

Mean Description of the Respondents' Concept and discipline techniques of parents a smart idea toward responsible parenthood in Terms of Educational Factors

EDUCATIONAL FACTORS	FREQUENCY n=45					MEAN	RANK	DESCRIPTION
	5	4	3	2	1			
1.I remind to my children that they should study hard	40	0	5	0	0	4.78	1	Always
2.I scold them when they got failed grade	7	5	4	7	22	2.29	7	Seldom
3.My children ask me permission when they go out to do their group project	28	3	10	2	2	4.18	3	Often
4.I didn't allow my children to absent in school	17	4	14	3	7	3.47	5	Often
5.I tell my children to get enough sleep on time so that he/she will not be late going to school	35	1	5	3	1	4.47	2	Always
6.I give my child reward when he/she is doing a good job in school	16	5	16	3	5	3.53	4	Often
7.I hug or kiss my children when they have done something well	15	5	13	6	6	3.38	6	Sometimes
Grand Weighted Mean						3.73		Often

This table indicates that parents always remind their children to study hard with the total mean of 4.78 because there is no parents who want their children to become nothing. In addition, education is the only thing that parents can give or legacy to their children to have a bright future someday.

Moreover, sometimes parents scold their children when they got failed grade with the total mean of 2.29 wherein it should not be. Instead of getting angry at a bad grade, parents should try and help their child figure out the best way for them to improve.

Table 8

Mean Description of the Respondents' Concept and discipline techniques of parents a smart idea toward responsible parenthood in Terms of Family Factors

FAMILY FACTORS	FREQUENCY n=45					MEAN	RANK	DESCRIPTION
	5	4	3	2	1			
1.I love my children	44	0	1	0	0	4.96	2	Always
2.I cared my children when they are sick	44	1	0	0	0	4.98	1	Always
3.I am being fair to my children	31	3	10	0	1	4.40	5	Always
4.When my children's quarrelling I discipline them both	34	1	9	1	0	4.51	3	Always
5.I teach my children not to be lazy in doing household chores	32	4	8	0	1	4.47	4	Always
6.I have a friendly talk with my child	23	5	13	2	2	4.00	6	Often
Grand Weighted Mean						4.55		Always

Parents have a big role when it comes to their children. One of this is parents always taking care their children when they are sick with the mean of 4.98 which you can appreciate the loved of parents because they don't want to suffer their children and it considered as the most challenging part for them. Thus, as parents they do everything they can to try and keep their kids from becoming ill or feeling pain.

In addition, parents often have friendly talk with their children with the total mean of 4.00 which it is the way of understanding.

Table 9

Mean Description of the Respondents' Concept and discipline techniques of parents a smart idea toward responsible parenthood in Terms of Peer Factors

PEER FACTORS	FREQUENCY n=45					MEAN	RANK	DESCRIPTION
	5	4	3	2	1			
1.I did not allow my children to go out with their friends just to go somewhere	9	5	19	8	4	3.16	4	Sometimes
2.I tell my children not to be friends from those who has bad attitude	24	0	12	5	4	3.78	2	Often
3.I did not allow my children to sleep on his/her friend's house	16	2	18	5	4	3.47	3	Often
4.I give an advice to my child when she/he has a problem regarding with friends	24	4	10	5	2	3.96	1	Often
Grand Weighted Mean						3.59		Often

This table shows the highest rank in which parents often give an advice to their child when she/he has a problem regarding with friends with the mean of 3.96. Moreover, parents also has part to their children life when it comes to friend's problem because parents is our friends too if children tell the issue concerning to his/her friends then they might listen to you and remind you so that the problem will be solve.

On the other hand, all parents want to protect their children which sometimes they didn't allowed their children to go out with their friends just to go somewhere with the total mean of 3.16 because they don't want their children to involve in doing such things that is not respectable that's why parents also don't want their children to be friends from those who are bad influence.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusion, and recommendation based on the analyses done in the previous chapter.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

1. What is the personal profile of the respondents?
 - a. Majority of the respondents belong to the age of 31-40 and 41-50 years old with the percentage of 37.78.
 - b. Majority of the respondents belong to the gender of female with the percentage of 77.78.
 - c. Majority of the respondents belong to the religion of Roman Catholic with the percentage of 80.
 - d. Majority of the respondents belong to the civil status of married with the percentage of 95.56.
 - e. Majority of the respondents belong to the home address of diamantina with the percentage of 44.44.

2. What are the concept and discipline techniques used by the parents for responsible parenthood in terms of:
 - a. In personal factors, majority of parents always teach their children good manner and right conduct with the mean of 4.89 because it is important in one's life. While, parents never slap their children when they have done something wrong with the mean of 1.73 because it is a harsh one.

 - b. In educational factors, majority of parents always remind their children to study hard with the mean of 4.78 because they want their children to become successful in the near future. While, parents seldom scold their children when they got failed grade with the mean of 2.29 but it should not be.

 - c. In family factors, majority of parents always cared their children when they are sick with the mean of 4.98 and it is the challenging part for them. While, parents often have a friendly talk with their child with the mean of 4.00 which it is a way of understanding.

 - d. In peer factors, majority of parents often give an advice to their child when she/he has a problem regarding with friends with the mean of 3.96. While, sometimes parents did not allow their children to go out with their friends just to go somewhere

with the mean of 3.16 because they don't want their children to involve in doing unnecessary things.

3. What is the importance of disciplining children?

Disciplining children is important as found in the result in which parents teach their children good manner and right conduct, teach not to be lazy in doing household chores, didn't allow their children to go out at night, drinking liquor and smoking to become respectful, well-behaved and responsible individual.

CONCLUSION

Based on the data gathered, we can assume the fact that the parents have their different techniques when it comes to disciplining their children whether in a positive or negative ways. Discipline is a process of teaching and guiding the children to have a good behavior as well as become respectful person. In the result shows that parents discipline their children in which they teach good manners and right conduct, remind their children to study hard, didn't allow to go out at night, and didn't tolerate their children fault. Those discipline techniques of parents is effective for children to have a moral character. However, on the other hand there are still parents who are out of control when children done something wrong which may involve angry and that's the time they used physical punishment rarely like spanking, and hitting which it should not be instead talk to your children about what he or she done and settle it because if that's the situation they might rebel and they will think you don't love them. Hence; discipline is an act of love, not anger.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby presented.

Children: As children, follow and obey the rules of parents because there is no parents who want their child become bad-mannered since parents always know best. Thus, be a good person and always bear in your heart and mind the lessons that you learn from your parents.

Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD): It is normal for children to commit an error but corporal punishment is not the right path to correct them. Thus, DSWD's provide equal and "may malasakit" (compassionate) service to the needy and protect the rights of the children, advocates for positive discipline.

Parents: As parents, for discipline techniques to be most effective there must be a positive, supportive, and loving relationship between your children in which

children feel loved and secure. Thus, parents must know the proper techniques in discipline the children when they have done something wrong in which understand that it's not socially acceptable to spank children instead talk calmly to have understanding.

Students: As students, follow the rules and regulation of the school. Thus, have a self- discipline so that the school will progress as well as possible in your studies in which to achieve your goal.

Subordinates: Obey the manager in the office or factories, don't be lazy in work and of course have a self- discipline to achieve the goal in a certain company.

Teachers: As a second mother of students, teacher must know the limitation in disciplining even if a student does not follow the rules still all students need to be treated with dignity. In addition, award certificates or simple sincere verbal praise can keep good behavior.

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